

Supplementary table 1

<p>Transcriptomic data: <i>Guy's, TCGA, METABRIC gene expression cohorts</i> (Fig. 1A, 1B, 1C, 5D; Suppl. Fig. 1, 2A, 2B, 4A, 4B)</p> <p><i>GEPIA cohort</i> (Tang <i>et. al.</i>) (Suppl. Fig. 3Ai, 3Bi, 4C)</p>	<p>Samples: Guy's: primary TNBC, N = 131; non-TNBC, N = 56 TCGA: primary TNBC, N = 112; non-TNBC, N = 578 METABRIC: primary TNBC, N = 101; non-TNBC, N = 1,096</p> <p>GEPIA: primary breast cancer, N = 1,085; normal breast, N = 291</p>
<p>Survival data: <i>KM plotter cohort</i> (https://kmplot.com/; Györfy <i>et. al.</i>) (Fig. 1D)</p>	<p>Samples: Primary breast cancer, N = 1,402</p>
<p>Protein expression data: <i>Human Protein Atlas cohort</i> (www.proteinatlas.org) Uhlen <i>et. al.</i> (Suppl Fig. 3Aii, 3Bii)</p>	<p>Samples: 24 normal human organs (immunohistochemical stainings of tissue sections from one to three healthy volunteer donors).</p>
<p>Cell line mRNA expression data: <i>Cancer Cell Line Encyclopedia (CCLE)</i> (https://sites.broadinstitute.org/ccle) Barretina <i>et. al.</i> (Fig. 2B)</p>	<p>Samples: CCLE database was used to characterize mRNA expression of <i>CDK2</i> in the eight TNBC cell lines used in this project.</p>

Supplementary Table 1. Summary of all internal and external cohorts used.

Supplementary Figure 1

Expression analyses of CDKs and cyclins involved in transcription regulation

Supplementary Figure 1. Gene expression level of transcription regulators in breast cancers.

Gene expression analysis of primary tumors from Guy's (TNBC-enriched, N = 177), TCGA (N = 578) and METABRIC (N = 1,197) cohorts of CDK and cyclin genes involved in transcription regulation. Color scale indicates log₂ expression values (yellow, higher; black, lower expression). Cohorts were divided into TNBC, ER+ and HER2+ groups based on their IHC-defined receptor status, in addition to PAM50 classification (Basal-like, HER2-enriched, luminal A, luminal B and normal-like).

Supplementary Figure 2

Supplementary Figure 2. Gene expression level of early phase cell cycle regulators in breast cancers.

Gene expression analysis of early phase cell cycle regulators in TCGA and Guy's cohorts classified by (A) PAM50 or (B) TNBC vs non-TNBC subtypes. Same as cyclin E and CDK2, the other early phase cell cycle regulators cyclin A (*CCNA1*), CDK4 (*CDK4*), CDK6 (*CDK6*) are all upregulated in basal-like/TNBC patients, although cyclin D (*CCND1*) were downregulated.

Supplementary Figure 3

(A) Cyclin E

(i) GEPIA mRNA expression

(ii) Human Protein Atlas protein expression

(B) CDK2

(i) GEPIA mRNA expression

(ii) Human Protein Atlas protein expression

Supplementary Figure 3. High cyclin E and CDK2 expression in breast tumors compared to normal tissues.

To compare between breast tumors expression level of (A) cyclin E or (B) CDK2 with normal tissues, (i) GEPIA mRNA expression data are shown for primary breast tumors (N = 1,085)

and normal breast tissues (N = 291), and (ii) Human Protein Atlas histology-based protein expression data are shown for major normal human tissues. Distribution of cyclin E and CDK2 in human organs are shown in 24 normal tissues. Immunohistochemical staining were performed from tissues of one to three healthy volunteer donors per tissue type, detection levels were classified as high, medium, low or not detected according to the staining intensity. Examples of the IHC-staining images are shown for vital human organs (lung, liver, kidney or heart). Data showed that both cyclin E and CDK2 were distributed in different organs mostly at low or medium levels (for cyclin E: 12 organs undetectable, 8 organs at low level, 4 organs at medium level; for CDK2: 8 organs undetectable, 10 organs at low level, 6 organs at medium level). All images are available from Human Protein Atlas version 19.3 (www.proteinatlas.org). Scale bar of representative images = 100 μ m.

Supplementary Figure 4

TCGA

(A) PAM50 subtypes

Guy's

TCGA

(B) TNBC/non-TNBC subtypes

Guy's

(C) GEPIA mRNA expression data

Supplementary Figure 4. Gene expression level of CDK7/cyclin H and CDK9/cyclin T in breast cancers.

SNS-032 inhibitor targeted CDK2, but also demonstrated activities against CDK7 and CDK9 in cell-free assay. Gene expression analysis of (A) PAM50 or (B) TNBC vs non-TNBC subtypes in both TCGA and Guy's cohorts showed downregulation of these two binding partners, CDK7/cyclin H and CDK9/cyclin T, in basal-like/TNBC patients, therefore no evidence of targeting these CDKs or cyclins for therapeutic strategies. (C) In addition, GEPIA data showed a small, but insignificant upregulation of CDK7 in breast tumors compared to normal breast tissues, however, cyclin H, CDK9 and cyclin T1 were all downregulated in breast cancers. Based on these data, normal tissue toxicity of SNS-032 should be low for those breast cancer patients, especially TNBC patients, with the downregulation of these genes.

Supplementary Figure 5

(A) PD-L1 expression in response to SNS-032 with IFN- γ *in vitro*

(B) IncuCyte Zoom Live-Imaging measurement of cell growth after Avelumab treatment, using purified NK cells as effector cells

IncuCyte – mCherry transfected tumor cells. Media contains:

IL2	10 U/ml
IL15	10 ng/ml
IFN- γ	10 ng/ml
Avelumab	10 μ g/ml

MDA-MB-231 = PD-L1-positive

MDA-MB-468 = PD-L1-negative

(C) Weight measurement of mice

End of experiment body weight lost (%)			
	-5%	-10%	-15%
DMSO	N = 4	1	1
SNS-032	0	0	0
Avelumab	4	3	1
SNS-032 + Avelumab	6	5	1

(N = number of mice in each treatment group with body weight lost)

Supplementary Figure 5. PD-L1 assessment in TNBC cells in preparation for *in vivo* combination therapy experiments.

(A) Flow cytometry analyses of MDA-MB-231 and Hs578T demonstrated PD-L1 upregulation after treated with IFN- γ for 48 hours (N = 3). PD-L1 expression in MDA-MB-468 remained at background level. (B) Avelumab enhanced NK cell-mediated cytotoxicity in PD-L1 expressing TNBC cells and prevented cell proliferation. Avelumab effect was confirmed *in vitro* by IncuCyte Zoom Live-Imaging tracking of mCherry-transfected TNBC cell growth, using purified NK cells as effector cells (one cancer cells to four NK cells ratio). MDA-MB-231 cells expressing PD-L1 were sensitive to avelumab (10 μ g/ml) and hence low cell count after 72 hours tracking, while PD-L1-negative MDA-MB-468 did not response to avelumab treatment. (C) Body weight measurement of the immunodeficient mice which received orthotopic (mammary fat pad) MDA-MB-231 cells together with human PBMC, and treated with SNS-032 or avelumab, or in combination, depicting lack of significant weight loss with tumor challenge, human immune cell engraftment and treatments.